
WRITING AS AN AIM AND MEANS OF TEACHING IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article examines methodological issues and principles determination of teaching writing in foreign language teaching, and also discusses the theoretical and methodological problems of teaching writing activities ways and types.

Keywords: *writing, teaching, foreign language, dictation, teacher, habit, visual, articulation, auding.*

Writing as a skill is very important in teaching and learning a foreign language. It helps pupils to assimilate letters and sounds of the English language, its vocabulary and grammar, and to develop habits and skills in pronunciation; speaking, and reading. The practical value of writing is great because it can fix patterns of all kinds (graphemes, words, phrases and sentences) in pupils' memory, thus producing a powerful effect on their mind. That is why the school syllabus reads: "Writing is a mighty means of teaching a foreign language." Writing includes penmanship, spelling, and composition. The latter is the aim of learning to write. The school syllabus states: "Pupils are expected to be able to write a letter in the foreign language within the material learnt." Since writing is a complicated skill it should be developed through the formation of habits such as:

- (1) the habit of writing letters of the English alphabet;
- (2) the habit of converting speech sounds into their symbols — letters and letter combinations;
- (3) the habit of correct spelling of words, phrases, and sentences;
- (4) the habit of writing various exercises which lead pupils to expressing their thoughts in connection with the task set.

In forming writing habits the following factors are of great importance:

1. Auditory perception of a sound, a word, a phrase, or a sentence, i.e., proper hearing of a sound, a word, a phrase, or a sentence.

2. Articulation of a sound and pronunciation of a word, a phrase, and a sentence by the pupil who writes.

3. Visual perception of letters or letter combinations which stand for sounds.

4. The movements of the muscles of the hand in writing. The ear, the eye, the muscles and nerves of the throat and tongue, the movements of the muscles of the hand participate in writing. And the last, but not the least, factor which determines progress in formation and development of lasting writing habits is pupils' comprehension of some rules which govern writing in the English language.

The teacher asks pupils to write first the letter, then the word in their exercise-books. When pupils are writing he walks round looking at the work they are doing and giving help to the pupils who need it. Since habits are formed and developed through performing actions, pupils are told to practice in writing the letter and the word (words) at home.

1. The teacher's handwriting and his skill in using the blackboard are of great importance. Children learn by imitating. Therefore the teacher's handwriting should be good enough to imitate. They usually write in the way the teacher does, so he must be-careful in the arrangement of the material on the blackboard because pupils will copy both what is written and how it is written. Consequently, training in penmanship implies: visual perception; observations accompanied by some explanations on the part of the teacher; practice under the teacher's supervision in class, and independently at home.

In spelling instruction the teacher should take into consideration the difficulties of English spelling and instruct pupils how to overcome these difficulties. The following exercises may be suggested for the purpose.

The additional work the pupil must perform in copying a text or an exercise makes him pay attention to the sound and meaning of the words. This kind of copying is a good way of ensuring the retention of the material. It must be extensively applied in the junior and in the intermediate stages.

2. Dictation. This kind of writing exercise is much more difficult than copying. Some methodologists think that it should never be given as a test to young beginners. "It is a means of fixing of what is already known, not a puzzle in which the teacher tries to defeat the pupil"(F. French).¹ Dictation is a valuable exercise because it trains the ear and the hand as well as the eye; it fixes in the pupil's mind the division of each sentence pattern, because the teacher dictates division by division. For example, *Tom and I go to school I together.*

Dictations can vary in forms and in the way they are conducted:

(a) **Visual dictation** as a type of written work is intermediate between copying and dictation. The teacher writes a word, or a word combination, or a sentence on the blackboard. The pupils are told to read-it and memorize its spelling. Then it is rubbed out and the pupils write it from memory.

(b) **Dictation drill** aims at consolidating linguistic material and preparing pupils for spelling tests. The teacher dictates a sentence. A word with a difficult spelling either is written on the blackboard, or is spelt by one of the pupils. Then the pupils are told to write the sentence. The teacher walks about the class and watches them writing. He asks one of the pupils who has written correctly to go to the blackboard and write the sentence for the other pupils to correct their mistakes if they have any. The dictation drill may be given for 10—12 minutes depending on the grade and the language material.

(c) **Self-dictation**. Pupils are given a text (a rhyme) to learn by heart. After they have learned the text at home the teacher, asks them to recite it. Then they are told to write it in their exercise-books from memory. So they dictate it to themselves. This type of written work may be given at junior and intermediate stages.

3. Writing sentences on a given pattern. This kind of writing exercise is more difficult because pupils choose words they are to use themselves. The following exercises may be suggested:

(a) Substitution: *Nick has a sister*. The pupils should use other words instead of *a sister*.

(b) Completion: *How many ... are there in the room? He came late because ...*

(c) Extension: *Ann brought some flowers*. (The pupils are expected to use an adjective before *flowers*.)

Practice of this kind can lead pupils to long sentences.

4. Writing answers to given questions. The question helps the pupil both with the words and with the pattern required for the answer.

The object of every kind of written exercise mentioned above is to develop pupils' spelling in the target language and to fix the linguistic material in their memory and in this way to provide favorable conditions for developing their skills in writing compositions. By composition in this case we mean pupils' expression of their own thoughts in a foreign language in connection with a suggested situation or a topic within the linguistic material previously assimilated in speech and reading. Progress in writing a foreign language is possible on condition that pupils have

adequate preparation for writing. This preparation should nearly always be carried out orally, except late at the senior stage when it can be done from books independently as at this stage oral questioning need not precede writing. Writing compositions will not help much in the learning of a new language without careful preparation. If pupils have to rack their brains for something to say, or if they try to express something beyond their powers, the writing may be more harmful than helpful. Preparation may include:

(a) oral questioning with the aim of giving the pupils practice in presenting facts and ideas in the target language;

(b) the use of pictures and other visual aids to provide information for written work;

(c) auding an extract or a story which can stimulate pupils' thought; after auding there should always be some questions on the content;

(d) silent reading which can be used as a source of information for pupils, first, to speak about, and then for writing. In teaching compositions the following exercises may be suggested:

1. A written reproduction of a story either heard or read. With backward classes most of the words that are habitually misspell must be written on the blackboard.

2. A description of a picture, an object or a situation. For example:

— Write not less than three sentences about (the object).

— Write five sentences about what you usually do after classes.

— Write four sentences about what you can see in the picture of the room.

3. A descriptive paragraph about a text, or a number of texts on a certain subject.

Pupils may be given concrete assignments. For instance:

— Describe the place where the action takes place.

— Write what you have learned about ...

— Write what new and useful information you have found for yourself in this text (these texts).

— Write what the author says about ... using the sentences from the text to prove it.

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